

A COMPARATIVE OF THE EFFICACY OF COMBINATION THERAPY WITH MYCOPHENOLATE MOFETIL(MMF) AND CALCINEURIN INHIBITORS(CNIs) AS STEROID SPARING AGENTS IN PEDIATRIC NEPHROTIC SYNDROME

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To evaluate and compare the effectiveness of two immunosuppressive regimens based on mycophenolate mofetil and tacrolimus in reducing relapse frequency and cumulative prednisolone dose

ABSTRACT

Nephrotic syndrome (NS) is one of the most common kidney diseases in childhood, with an incidence of 2–7 per 100,000 children and a prevalence of approximately 16 per 100,000. The syndrome is characterized by massive proteinuria (>3.5 g/1.73 m²/day), hypoalbuminemia (<25 g/L), generalized edema, and hyperlipidemia. While 80–90% of cases are steroid-sensitive, a significant proportion develop steroid dependence (SDNS) or frequently relapsing NS (FRNS). Long-term corticosteroid exposure causes severe adverse effects, including growth retardation, obesity, hypertension, bone demineralization, and metabolic disturbances. Therefore, steroid-sparing immunosuppressive agents play a vital role in disease control and toxicity minimization.

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Objective: To evaluate and compare the effectiveness of two immunosuppressive regimens based on mycophenolate mofetil and tacrolimus in reducing relapse frequency and cumulative prednisolone dose.

Methods: A prospective study included 89 children with frequently relapsing nephrotic syndrome. Patients received either mycophenolate mofetil + tacrolimus + prednisolone (n=34) or mycophenolate mofetil + prednisolone (n=55). Clinical outcomes included relapse rate and cumulative steroid dose.

Results: Relapse rate decreased from 6.7 to 2.0 in the triple-therapy group and from 3.9 to 0.9 in the double-therapy group. Cumulative prednisolone dose decreased from 9516 mg to 3743 mg and from 9548 mg to 2458 mg, respectively.

Conclusion: Both regimens significantly reduce relapse frequency and steroid exposure. Combination therapy with tacrolimus was used in a more severe cohort of patients with a high initial relapse rate. Mycophenolate-based therapy is an effective steroid-sparing strategy in children with frequently relapsing nephrotic syndrome. In practical terms, MMF requires simpler laboratory monitoring (CBC + biochemistry), while CNIs need therapeutic drug level monitoring to avoid nephrotoxicity. For pediatric nephrotic syndrome in resource-limited healthcare systems, MMF represents a clinically effective, well-tolerated, and logistically feasible alternative to CNI-based regimens.

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